

THE VIEW OF HO CHI MINH IN TRAINING TEACHER IN THE BASIC EFFECTIVE RENEWAL OF EDUCATION IN VIETNAM TODAY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10973273>

Published Date: 15-April-2024

Abstract: During the history of the nation, teachers always play an important role in the social life of the country. Thus, building the teachers who are not only skilled, professional, dedicated and committed but also be constantly renewed and creative in education, are the key points for the development of education in particular, and the development of the country in general. Started from the above meaning, in this article, from the presentation of Ho Chi Minh's views of educating teacher, the author pointed out some requirements for educating the teacher to meet the changing requirements of new basic, comprehensive renewal in today education.

Keywords: Ho Chi Minh, educating teacher, the basic, comprehensive renewal in education, Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam, undergone more than 30 years of national renewal, and over 30 years of education and training, has made important changes in order to meet better the requirements of the development of the country and people of Vietnam. It is the need for the internal development of the nation, and also it is the golden opportunity for Vietnam to be able to compare with the wealthy nation in the world in the context of globalization and integration of the world economy.

In the history of the development of Vietnamese education, especially in each step of the fundamental and comprehensive reform of Vietnamese education from the 6th Congress (12/1986) to the 11th Congress (01/2011) of the Party, Ho Chi Minh's ideology and philosophy have been playing an important position and crucial role. Thanks to the foundation of Ho Chi Minh's ideas and philosophies, the education sector, each institution, each person, every individual involved in the education could find the lessons, the aims, useful practical methods to manipulate, study, adjust themselves correctly. Since then, it brings high educational efficiency and meeting the demands and requirements of education - training people for the revolution.

2. CONTENT

1. The view of Ho Chi Minh of educating teacher

On the basis of the Marxist-Leninist view, "the educator himself must be educated", Ho Chi Minh pointed out the requirements and tasks for the teachers. With the new demands and tasks that the fundamental and comprehensive renewal of the country's education system is questioning, President Ho Chi Minh's educational ideas and direction are always the brightest torches enlightening the way for "self-education" of each modern master.

First of all, each teacher must be deeply aware of his position and role, must follow the guideline "Study, study, study forever", it means constantly changing the content, teaching methods, to study for life, to become an open system of knowledge, avoid stereotypes, backwardness, old thinking, cliché and consistent principles: taking students at the center of the educational process. According to Ho Chi Minh, no teacher, no education. To be worthy of that title, he argues that each teacher must constantly study, cultivate professional, and moral virtues, revolutionary morality, both "Hong" and "Chuyen", "have to progress in time for catching up the modern life to accomplish the task". Apart from reminding about academic study, Ho Chi Minh noted a very important issue of political learning. According to him, the new educators have strengthened the revolutionary morality, to do well the work that the Party and the people entrusted. On the other hand, Ho Chi Minh said that the teacher himself must learn from the real life. Because Ho Chi Minh is a person who attaches importance to combining theory with reality, attaching realities and tasks to teaching and training human beings. In order to improve the quality of education, each teacher must constantly train in the practical realities of social life. From there, bringing new knowledge to serve the learners, enriching their knowledge, helping them to draw knowledge and lessons for the future.

Secondly, in the educational method, Ho Chi Minh emphasized that the education has to base on the need of students. Education must lay on the academic level, living habits, the cognition level, the experience of the contest, the practical status of people. In education, He required it must be combined with many educational formats, no absolute any education format. He wrote: "In education, if even students have a good school but missing education in family and society, the results of education is not completed" [3, page.591]. In front of the need of modern education, learners often want to approach the newest contents and advanced technologies of the world, the educators themselves have to know and utilize effectively the high-tech educational technologies and machines to meet the need of information and knowledge of each level of education. From there, it helps the education process to be effective and suitable for the practical needs of learners, institutions and importantly for the needs of the modern labor market. These are practical standards for current education and training. If these things are completed then the educator could have an effective example for learners. This method must be carried out on all three aspects of "spiritual, material and cultural" [3, p.591]. With the requirements of the education and moral improvement of the young generation, the method of setting a good example of teachers is more meaningful in the fundamental renewal of teaching and learning in our country.

Thirdly, the teacher must be the person who perceives, organizes and operates democracy in education. At every stage of the revolution, Ho Chi Minh particularly interested in education in general, and promoting democracy in school education in particular, to train human resources and talents to serve the country. This is also one of the requirements of "promoting socialist democracy" to "turn an ignorant country into a highly educated country and a joyful and happy life." It is clear that by just only promoting democracy to the highest level, we can encourage all students and students to come up with ideas. In this position, the role of the educator as well as the school is very important in creating a democratic mechanism in education.

First and foremost, Ho Chi Minh considered that the teachers must have a straight, unimposed point of view and to create an environment, condition for the learning and the learning of the user, could discuss and exchange while teaching and learning. He emphasized that in school must have democracy. To be more specific, he wants lecturer must respect the opinion of colleges, students, should not have prejudice to left opinion, must highlight the independent manners in free mind, etc. it must remove the remained effect of enslavement education of colonist, for instance: indifferent attitude to society, left always from working and struggling life of people, learn to obtain certification, teach in a stuffed way. It needs to construct the thought: teaching and learning to serve nation and people [3, p.185].

In the background of integration of Vietnamese education today, the democracy in education needs to be absorbed in the minds of every educator, every department has to educate, every school has to educate so that the issue of "democracy in education" will become a natural thought of teachers. For learners, if they have "democracy in education" and know how to manipulate and exercise that democratic right, then the new educational process can be a positive two-way relationship, contributing to the new forms of Vietnamese education; creating a democratic style for the new socialist people.

On the other hand, for the guideline "democracy in education" to be implemented effectively, Ho Chi Minh asserted that it was impossible for excessive or arbitrary democracy, that democracy must be linked to law, and freedom must be attached to Discipline. In addition to have the implementation of democracy in school education, the teacher needs the interaction between the teacher and the learner, creating a democratic atmosphere or a true democratic environment in

each lesson, must organize for students to have the sense of mastery, effort to study and research, promote the spirit of self-learning to constantly renew and perfect themselves to be worthy as future force of the nation.

Fourthly, the teachers in Ho Chi Minh educational theory should consider self-study as a long-lasting process for themselves, and it is an important and crucial educational method. In the face of the increasing demands of practical education and of the educational objects, the teachers must construct for themselves the abilities and qualities that are necessary to meet the demands of the new situation. Therefore, apart from constantly cultivating moral, dedicated to the cause of human cultivation, the teacher must always cultivate the ability to self-study and self-learning methods to improve themselves, increase knowledge, complete personality. Because of the industrialization and modernization of the country with the explosion of information technology, of new knowledge and materials, of the innovations that can change the world, the expansion of new occupations in the future, etc it requires each educator to have the abilities for self-study, self-research to adapt to the demands of the diversity of the educational environment and the demand the learner and the whole society.

Therefore, the teachers must become the model of self-study. Since that point, it spreads out and evokes the spirit of self-learning, self-conscious, self-renewal of learners; The educational process aims at "learning the real thing" and creates the basis for creativity in the acquisition of knowledge and the ability to solve the new problems of current national development practice. Through this, it provides benefits to the learner, the community, and the whole society. Thus, Vietnamese labour force has a chance to improve to the advanced levels, meeting better the demands of the open domestic labour environment and reaching out to the international level.

Ho Chi Minh's ideas, methods, and philosophies in education are the foundation and the guideline for the fundamental and comprehensive reform of Vietnamese education. The instructions and especially his examples of education are the indispensable lessons for every educator in the process of integrating into the international education of Vietnam.

2. Training the teachers to meet the requirements of basic and comprehensive renewal of Vietnamese education today

In the trend of integration, globalization of Vietnamese education, the role of teachers in implementing the goals of education and training is very important. This will be the force that is directly involved in the educational process; they are the people who will approach, direct the thought, and convey knowledge to learners; They are the people who have access to world advanced educational content and methods to promote the fast and sustainable development of Vietnamese education; They are also the force that constructs and implements the policies and guidelines of the Party and the State in each particular situation of education to contribute to the current model of education. They directly lead the basis for the formation of a new human personality - global citizens who have appreciated abilities and characters to accomplish successfully the political, economic, cultural and social missions of the country.

The resolution no 29 of "On fundamental and comprehensive renewal of education and training to meet the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the background of socialist-oriented market economy and international integration" of The Party Central Committee, is a large-scale program of strategic importance in human development aims at bringing the country to a fast and sustainable development in the face of the challenges posed by the era to the whole human race. From the evaluation of the development of education and training in the period of industrialization and modernization, and pointing out the causes, the Resolution outlined seven guiding principles, including the implementation of "Education Development and training is to improve people's knowledge, training human resources, cultivating talents. Strongly transform the education process from the predominantly knowledge-based to the comprehensive development of the learner's qualities and qualities "[1], aiming to the goal:" Making the fundamental changes in terms of quality and efficiency in education and training; To better meet the needs of constructing, defending the Fatherland and learning needs of the people. Educating the Vietnamese people to develop comprehensively and bring into full play the potentials and creativity of each individual; love the family, love the country, love the people; Live well and work effectively "[1]. Completing this goal, it is the task, the responsibility of the education sector and the teachers in more specific.

In particular, in light of the new requirements and missions of Vietnam from now to 2020, the XII National Party Congress (2016) once again emphasized the key goals and tasks of basic and comprehensive renewal of education. The Party Congress defined this term as "fundamental and comprehensive renewal of education and training towards

openness, integration to build learning society; developing comprehensively capacity, physical health, morality, lifestyle, sense of respect for law and civic responsibility, etc". "Reform the curriculum framework, pay more attention to the need of improving life skills, reduce the load on content in the general education" [6, p.27].

So, in the renovation of the country, the central point of educational renewal, the people who will play the main role in the educational reformation taking this to success, is the teachers. They will be the pioneers, the essential part and the force that contributes directly to the renewal of education. Hence, firstly, each teacher must realize clearly their role. From that, they could determine their responsibilities in education to meet the requirement of basic and comprehensive renewal of Vietnamese education in the face of deeply and widely integration today.

At the same time, in order to meet the requirements of the growing social reality, especially with the increasing demands of the educated person, the teacher must be fully educated.

From the awareness of their responsibilities in the process of renovating teaching, learning contents and methods as well as the urgent requirements of the new educational system, each teacher have to constantly cultivate the professional subjects to meet the requirements of raising the quality of education and training; consider the importance of moral education, lifestyle, creative capacity, practical skills and ability to make a living; always grasp thoroughly the learner-centered principle in the teaching process, follow the process of relating between theory and practice.

Especially, in the background of the 4.0 Industrial Revolution, with its remarkable achievements in science and technology and in artificial intelligence, robots are increasingly intelligent, able to remember, learn more and more. It is laying down new requirements for teachers who carry out the mission of "cultivating people" to train high-quality human resources for the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country. Apart from their professional capabilities, they need to have exceptional abilities, be able to work with smart technology and language ability to gain access to the world in order to take advantages from the opportunities of this revolution. When the 4.0 Industrial Revolution develops exponentially and the changes in technology which occur daily, affect directly the field of education (the choice of learning field, occupation; the method and the way of teaching, etc), it requires teachers to be adaptable and able to solve problems in flexible, creative ways. Practicing skills such as: solving problems arising in educational activities logically, teamwork, adaptive skills, ability to improve self, ability to work continuously, the ability to use smart technology, social skills and creativity in the global environment. They are considered to be the key factors to the success of today's education.

On the other hand, the teacher must be a self-taught model because "learning never end up". Particularly, in a "flat world" as now, when the knowledge resource of the human being is constantly multiplying every second, every minute, the abilities of teachers must grow up strongly, endless efforts, self-training to meet the requirements of the career of growing people and responding to the desire of society. It is because the teacher is always considered by society as a cultural symbol, representing the civilization of the era.

It could be recognized that education in Vietnam during the development process, especially in the background of the current, is lacking the high-quality human resources. This has been a major limitation of the education sector in developing the highly qualified workforce to meet the requirements of industrialization, modernization and international integration of the nation. While the Party and the State define that knowledge economy is the trigger for sustainable development, the purpose and content of education reform should be focused on finding ways to develop productive forces in order to be adaptable and furthermore, to create motivation for social - economic development. This issue was once again seriously recognized by the XIII National Party Congress and affirmed by the focus on building high-level faculty; To increase investment in material foundations on the basis of socialization of education; Job-related training and social needs are an urgent task and solution to ensure the success of this educational innovation.

3. CONCLUSION

From the view of Ho Chi Minh, each teacher has to find a path, get new content and methods in approaching education and innovating the teaching-learning process. Teachers must always be creative and active in solving new requirements which arise from the reality of education so that education is the means for human development and the consolidation of human rights;

Education has to support the need of social-economic development of the country, heighten people as the subject of the socialist-oriented reform process. As Minister Phung Xuan Nha said, "We have to transfer an education which focused on receive contents is the mainstream to an education that focuses on teaching methods and skills on the basis of professional knowledge to develop the capacity of learners and teach human dignity. Education is not about qualifications, but about human well-being". Thus, the responsibility of each teacher becomes more and nobler and worthy in realizing the goal of training new socialist people for the prosperous development of the nation in the new era.

REFERENCES

- [1] The Communist Party of Vietnam, Resolution of the 8th National Conference on XI "*on fundamental and comprehensive reform of education and training to meet the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the background of the market economy and international integration.*"
- [2] Communist Party of Vietnam (2016), *Document of the 12th National Party Congress*, Office of the Party Central Committee, Hanoi.
- [3] *Ho Chi Minh* (2011), Full set, Volume 10, National Political Publishing House, Hanoi.
- [4] Hoang Thuy, "*Minister Phung Xuan Nha: the goal of education is not the certification*" Vnexpress.net, April, 10th 2016